

FACTOR ANALYSIS OF RECENT YOUTH SOCIO-POLITICAL VOCABULARY**Guliyeva Lyudmila***Senior teacher of the chair "Russian and eastern languages"
Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The article scrutinizes extralinguistic, intralinguistic and semi-linguistic factors that influence the political lexicon of the youngsters. The words of actual political discourse have been classified into several sections which have been spelled out in the article. Methodology is based on the survey conducted among the schoolchildren of 9-11 grades. The list of lexemes was divided into 3 main subgroups which were common vocabulary, terminological vocabulary and slang vocabulary. The terms have been analyzed in terms of extralinguistic, intralinguistic and semi-linguistic factors in the study. The study underlines that one word might be polysemantic depending on which terminology it refers to. One technical term may have a vulgar meaning in some cases for its sphere of usage.

Keywords: extralinguistic, intralinguistic, socio-political vocabulary, slang, discourse

Introduction

In order to clarify how extralinguistic and intralinguistic factors can impact the youth political lexicon, we will analyze the materials we have chosen. Some culture-bound terms are not translated and remain how they are [6]. Accepting the classification established in the scientific community, we considered the following thematic groups of socio-political vocabulary, identified by A.I.Dyakov: the words of the actual political discourse [1]:

- a) nomenclature names - persons (officials), departments, bodies, etc.;
- b) territories;
- c) terminology of electoral and related technologies (political marketing, etc.);
- d) names of political parties, movements, trends and their members (participants);
- e) political jargon;
- f) terms of law used in socio-political discourse; mass media:
- g) the actual terms;
- h) legal jargon;
- i) economic terms used in the socio-political discourse of the media;
- j) religious terms used in the socio-political discourse of the media;
- k) ethnographic terms used in the socio-political discourse of the media;
- l) technical terms denoting realities of great social significance;
- m) philosophical, cultural, sociological, linguistic and psychological terms denoting realities of great social significance.

Methodology

We conducted surveys among schoolchildren (students of grades 9-11) and students and selected lexical units that were influenced by internal and external factors and reflect various trends in the language. The messages of users of youth social networks on the Internet, in which socio-political vocabulary was used, were also analyzed [7].

After questioning groups of schoolchildren and students and analyzing comments on the Internet, we compiled the following list of lexemes (120 pieces), which we divided into three main subgroups: common

vocabulary, terminological vocabulary and slang vocabulary [3]. Separately (with an asterisk), we marked the words related to journalistic jargon [12].

Common vocabulary: power, freedom, censorship, war, taxes, propaganda, corruption, opposition, party, president, parliament, deputy, duma, elections, mayor, city hall, regime, democracy, migrants, sanctions, rally, patriot, patriotism, voter, course, liberal, leader, curtain, budget, protest, boycott, bribe, agenda, arena, political prisoner, reform, headquarters, program, crisis, interests, collusion, falsification, repression, riot police, arrest, search, process, constitution, tyranny, despotism, terrorism, coup, special services, state employees, beneficiaries, pro-government, pro-government, pro-Western, pro-Ukrainian, loosen, junta, conspiracy, aggravation, superpower;

Terminological vocabulary: geopolitics, speaker, values, electorate, liberalism, declarations, totalitarianism, neutrality, picket, renovation, privatization, populism, referendum, affiliated, lustration, state contract, investment, tender, annexation, offshore, lobby, lobby, escalation, politicization, appeal, feudalism, Islamism, conspiracy theorist;

Slang: primaries, cubes, cut, throw-in, throw-in, roundabouts, screw, paddy wagon, lawlessness, drank, boyars, tsar, national Bolsheviks, quilted jacket, quilted work, cotton wool, embroidery, bandera, the Kremlin, krymnashist, liberalist, potsreot, volunteer, package, braces, sofa, scoop, maïdan. Different methods including GTM [11] and CLT [9] can be applied to teach these terms [10].

Data Analysis

The lexical units we are considering, for the most part, have a nominative character. Nouns make up more than 90% of the total number of lexemes (slightly less than 10% form verbs and adjectives, participles). When questioning, the respondents often indicated not individual lexemes, but phraseological combinations (for example, not "values", but "traditional values", not "arena", but "international arena", etc.).

We believe this is due to speech clichés that are well-established in political discourse, which in turn reflect the peculiarities of human perception: the epithet – "traditional" - is a reflection of the country's political course (i.e., an extralinguistic factor operates here).

As for the combination “international arena”, we see in it the need to remove the ambiguity of the pivotal word “arena” by concretizing it with an epithet. The very use of this word is based on metaphorization (an arena is a place of public competitions; according to J.Lakoff and M.Johnson, disputes, including international ones, are often described by the metaphor “a dispute is a war”), which we called a manifestation of the extralinguistic influence of features human perception.

In each of these groups of vocabulary, we analyzed the impact of factors influencing the evolution of the language. We also analyzed the impact of external and internal factors on each of the selected lexemes. It should be noted that some difficulty was caused by the differentiation of vocabulary between the groups of common and terminological. This is due to the trend towards the movement of meanings from stylistically marked to more neutral ones, which is characteristic of socio-political vocabulary in general (the influence of the semi-linguistic factor).

Discussion

The frequency of mentioning certain lexemes turned out to be interesting. So, for example, in the student group, which consisted mainly of people aged 23-26, such lexemes as “war”, “city hall”, etc. were more often mentioned. In the group of high school students and junior students (17-22), the most popular lexemes were “corruption” and “opposition”. In our opinion, this most clearly emphasizes the dependence of youth socio-political vocabulary on extralinguistic factors, in this case, on the age of the respondents, the sociocultural environment in which they are their political preferences, the influence of the media and the speech activity of authoritative personalities, etc.

Intralinguistic factors influence this lexeme not as actively as external ones. As we have already noted, the analysis of the influence of intralinguistic factors requires consideration of larger time intervals than the one we have chosen in this paper. However, one can see the influence of the tendency to abstract the meaning of the word. Corruption is perceived as “global evil”, “absolute evil”, “root of evil”, “social evil”, etc., it is considered “global” and “unstoppable” (real media headlines are reflected). In these examples, we can observe the removal of the stylistic marking of the word (although dictionaries give it with the mark bookish, we see that it tends to move into the category of common vocabulary), which, as we have already noted, according to linguists (in particular, A.A.Polikarpov), is a particular manifestation of the action of the factor stated above (i.e., the tendency to abstract the meaning of the word) [8].

The remaining lexemes were analyzed by us in a similar way. Let us dwell on some examples of the influence of external and internal factors, which seemed to us quite indicative.

It can be argued that among the internal factors, the factor of saving efforts has shown itself quite clearly: there are abbreviations generated by compressive word formation, abbreviations of words (media, Russian Orthodox Church, National Bolsheviks, state contract, etc.); short foreign words are borrowed, the

Russian equivalent of which is too long; (brexit, primaries, etc.), the number of verbal nouns with the meaning of action (stuffing) is increasing. Some words bear the anthroponomastic features [4].

The words “screw”, “carousels”, etc. also reveal a tendency to polysemy under the influence of extralinguistic factors (and the very ability of words to detect this tendency is an intralinguistic factor). The influence of the realities of the surrounding world is expressed in these words by metaphorizing the meaning: the main meaning of the word “screw” is turning a screw, screw, bolt, etc. along a thread, thread, screw it in or turn it out. The figurative meaning in which the word exists in the political lexicon of young people (participants in rallies, protest movements, etc.) is to grab someone using physical violence, deprive them of freedom of movement, twist. Besides, the word “screw” has a vulgar meaning, as well [5].

The word form “carousels” is the plural of the word “carousel” (from Italian *carosello*, from *carro* “wagon” + *sello* “saddle”), which has the main meaning: an entertainment attraction, a rotating platform with seats in the form of horses, boats, etc. n. for skating. This lexical-semantic variant tends to be used in the plural, and it is possible that with the disintegration of polysemy, it will move into the category of pluralia tantum. We trace the influence of the intralinguistic factor in the elimination of excessive synonymy. In this regard, the history of the word is interesting: “referendum”, denoting a popular vote on any important issue for the life of the country.

There is also a synonymous word “plebiscite” in the language, but it is used much less frequently in modern political discourse. We traced the dynamics of these words in the National Corpus of the Russian Language: We found that the word “referendum” is becoming more and more popular (this is also influenced by the extralinguistic factor associated with political processes in the world), and the word “plebiscite” is disappearing.

There is also a change in the meanings of words that belonged to the political slang of the previous era. For example, the word “sofa”, in our opinion, a kind of slang homonyms representing the significative aspect of the meaning of the lexeme “sofa”. The adjective sofa in the 90s usually referred to the word “party”, and this combination meant “a party whose members can all fit on one sofa.” With the disappearance of the political phenomenon, this lexeme moved into the category of historicisms, and sofa is now a synonym for the slang word kitchen that existed in Soviet times and denotes a person who loves to talk about politics, but does not understand it (sofa expert, sofa troops, sofa politician). This term may cause some challenges while learning [2].

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note once again that the influence of extralinguistic and intralinguistic factors should not be considered separately from each other, but in combination this approach reflects the very essence of the language, the unity of the content plan and the expression plan. The classification proposed by us is to a certain extent conditional and cannot be considered

complete, but nevertheless, due to the lack of development of the topic and the lack of a single clear terminological basis in linguistics for studying the concept of “factors influencing the evolution of a language”, it can be considered the initial stage in the development of this material.

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